

Empowering Learners for Inclusive Use of AI

Siyuan Li¹, Scotty D. Craig², and Punya Mishra³

Arizona State University, Tempe, USA
{siyuanmeimei, Scotty.Craig, punya.mishra}@asu.com

Abstract. Domain-independent non-cognitive capabilities are crucial for empowering individuals, especially disadvantaged populations, to effectively utilize AI for studying, working, and living in the face of rapid technological advancements. However, students are not effectively prepared on the necessary skills and knowledge for lifelong learning or effective collaboration between humans and machines. We propose three related research topics (DEIB promotion, ethical issues, and student preparedness) that explore effective solutions to empower learners for inclusive use of AI in diverse learning conditions. Our aim is to understand learner needs and contextual factors influencing solution implementation, promoting dialogue and interdisciplinary collaboration.

Keywords: Non-cognitive development, Inclusive Use of AI, Interdisciplinary collaboration

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly revolutionizing education, providing a multitude of benefits, including improved teaching [17] and learning [22] outcomes. The integration of AI in education (AIED) presents numerous advantages including improved student engagement through analyzing facial movement [18], more efficient and personalized assessment by providing real-time feedback [16, 33], better collaboration and communication by analyzing gaze patterns [1], and more streamlined administrative processes using automated essay scoring systems [24].

2 DEIB in AIED

In response to the persistent exposure of systemic biases and injustices, Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Belonging (DEIB) have gained considerable attention in organizations in recent years [9]. DEIB refers to creating an environment where individuals from diverse backgrounds feel valued and respected, have equitable access to opportunities, and can fully participate in society. Ultimately, such efforts aim to foster an inclusive environment where everyone can feel a sense of belonging [40].

With the various affordances of AI in education, it is important to ensure that AI is developed and implemented with a focus on DEIB [28]. Some researchers have

proposed frameworks and guidance for designing AIED systems that promote DEIB [8, 22, 27], while others have developed practical approaches for integrating DEIB into AIED systems [2, 4].

[8] classified the ethical considerations of using AI in education into upstream and downstream factors, identifying five distinct yet interconnected areas within these factors: access, representation, algorithms, interpretations, and citizenship. They further discussed specific ethical problems within each area and suggested collaborative efforts from a variety of stakeholders to solve these problems. For example, to solve problems related to data-based decision-making (e.g., insufficient, out-of-context, and fragmentary), it is recommended to increase data diversity and contextualization [19]. All non-technical stakeholders, such as educators and policymakers, must participate and reflect on the algorithmic development process to eliminate bias, gain a basic understanding of the processes involved, ask critical ethical questions to developers and providers, and support transparency in data collection and algorithmic development [15, 32].

Similarly, [30] proposed competence frameworks to enhance Educational Data Literacy (EDL) skills to promote effective and ethical use of data in online and blended teaching and learning practices among educational organizations and professionals. [27] proposed a heuristic cognitive framework for the development of inclusive and equitable AIED including 1) identification of the intended beneficiaries of any AIED applications; 2) active involvement of all stakeholders in co-participating throughout the iterative design cycle; 3) proactive identification of any potential harms and biases of AIED tools, and 4) engagement in accountability-focused measurement of AIED efficacy.

[4] summarized tools and approaches used to pursue DEI education, including the use of art-based training [4] and simulation [5] to cultivate cultural humility, evidence-based questionnaires (Implicit Association Test (IAT)) to measure unconscious bias [10], and mentorship and career development programs (the National Research Mentoring Network (NRMN)) to increase the diversity of biomedical research [11]. [2] suggested appointing a Digital Ethics Officer (DEO) as an Educational Technology unit of the Higher Education Institution to address ethical considerations in digital teaching and data use.

In general, studies on DEIB dimensions of AIED emphasize the importance of establishing and executing ethical frameworks for diversity, equity, and inclusion in AI-driven educational technologies. Meaningful interdisciplinary conversations are needed to develop students' cognitive and non-cognitive capabilities. These discussions should explore both high-tech and low-tech solutions tailored to learner needs and specific environmental factors. To promote dialogue, we explore some illustrative questions: (1) What challenges exist in promoting DEIB in AIED settings? (2) What are strategies for addressing related ethical issues? (3) What are the key factors for preparing students' capabilities for the inclusive use of AI?

3 Challenges in Promoting DEIB in AIED

However, promoting diversity, equity, inclusion, and belonging (DEIB) in the field of artificial intelligence in education (AIED) faces significant challenges. One of the challenges is the limited research on ethics and social justice-related topics within the AIED community, which raises questions about the community's values and priorities [13, 40]. While various discussions have centered around ethical AI guidelines and frameworks, the absence of consistent and shared theoretical foundations in the development and implementation of AIED tools remains a significant challenge [35]. The lack of common theoretical foundations results in an absence of consensus on the definitions, objectives, methodologies, and evaluation criteria required to advance DEIB in AIED. This, in turn, may hinder the efficacy of collective DEIB efforts within the AIED community [40].

4 Strategies for Addressing Ethical Issues in AIED

By analyzing student data and behavior, AIED systems can provide personalized recommendations and feedback to help students achieve their learning goals [14]. However, there are several ethical concerns associated with these practices including privacy [21, 25], bias and equity [12], autonomy [34, 39], accountability [23], explainability [3], and trustworthiness [31]. The research indicated that the lack of student involvement in decision-making regarding learning analytics impedes the effective implementation and adoption of these technologies in educational settings [26, 37]. For instance, [26] have summarized that the ineffective adoption of learning analytics can be attributed to several factors, including students' inadequate understanding of learning analytics usage, a lack of connection between students and faculty, a low perceived usefulness of the dashboards, and limited individual agency in utilizing the recommended learning support.

The application of human-centered design principles and approach is crucial when utilizing student data, and incorporating learner-centeredness is a key aspect of human-centered design in the application of student data. [36] developed PANDORA, a checklist framework for addressing ethical considerations in learning analytics, covering dimensions such as Privacy, Autonomy, Non-probabilistic algorithms, Duty to act, Openness and transparency, Resolve data ownership, and All stakeholders.

Moreover, the applications of AIED involve a trade-off between accuracy and transparency, and various stakeholders may weight them differently [13]. In response, recent efforts have focused on creating Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) systems to address ethical concerns of AI systems by providing users with understandable explanations about AI processes [3]. [30] presented a three-layer framework that establishes a connection between the objectives of designing XAI systems and the techniques utilized to assess them. This framework includes that experts evaluate performance and outcomes, users assess the interface for understandability and user-friendliness, and machine learning algorithms are evaluated

for accuracy and trustworthiness. These iterative evaluations foster a trust relationship between users and AI systems.

5 Preparing Students with the Capabilities for Inclusive AI Use

The fear of being replaced by AI has intensified with the widespread usage of large language models such as GPT. However, the actual concerns should focus on how humans can collaborate with AI in manners that augment their intelligence and enhance their overall wellbeing [7]. Modern human decision-making is a socio-technical collaborative process where humans are enabled to integrate their values with AI-generated insights to accomplish their objectives [31]. As a phrase from the internet goes, "AI will not replace you, but someone who uses AI will." However, due to disparities in the availability and accessibility of AI education and training programs, historically underserved populations most likely be placed at a disadvantageous position by this trend.

The inadequacy of the education systems in keeping pace with AI advancements poses a challenge to sufficiently equip learners (particular disadvantaged learners) with the requisite skills and knowledge for lifelong learning, successful citizenship, and effective human-machine collaboration [20]. Thus, it is critical to prioritize the development of domain-independent capabilities, enabling individuals to pursue personalized goals and values through informed and responsible actions, instead of focusing solely on the acquisition of domain-specific skills and knowledge [31].

Researchers have acknowledged the inconsistency in the terminology used to describe non-epistemic domain-independent capabilities, such as non-cognitive skills, 21st-century skills, and social-emotional learning [20, 34]. A team of 11 interdisciplinary researchers led a polylogue initiative to collectively develop knowledge on the human capabilities for an AI-empowered world [20]. They recommended using the term "capabilities" instead of more narrow terms like "literacy," "skills," or "competencies" to encompass the potential, dispositions, and opportunities individuals have to pursue specific values and outcomes. Capabilities span from those focus on individual behavior and cognition (i.e., self-regulation, creativity) to those related to a joint and relational sensemaking (i.e., cultural and situational awareness).

Thus, there is an increasing need to develop holistic learning solutions with evidence-based multidimensional metrics to assess learner success in both cognitive and non-cognitive capabilities [38]. Prioritizing learner diversity and environmental factors throughout the conceptualization, operationalization, implementation, and evaluation of these metrics enables individuals to embark on a self-directed lifelong learning journey, actively engage with diverse knowledge, participate in meaningful dialogues, navigate the evolving landscape of AI technology, promote inclusivity, and thrive amidst rapid technological advancements.

In conclusion, our study explored three key topics in promoting DEIB in AIED settings including challenges of DEIB promotion, ethical issues of AIED systems, and student preparedness for inclusive AI use. Promoting DEIB faces challenges due to

limited research and inconsistent theoretical foundations, hindering collective efforts. Thus, The AIED community should foster a core commitment to DEIB and promote meaningful interdisciplinary and cross-cultural conversations to collectively advance DEIB principles. Additionally, ethical concerns in AIED systems require learner-centered design and explainable AI (XAI) to ensure transparency, user-friendliness, and trust. To cultivate an inclusive AI future, preparing students for inclusive AI use through the development of domain-independent non-cognitive capabilities is essential. Empowering learners to actively engage in co-designing, co-developing, and collaborating on AIED technologies places them at the heart of this transformative journey.

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